

Parental Involvement in Pupils Learning as a Correlate of Academic Achievement of Primary School Pupils in Anambra State

Chinyelu Nwokolo (Prof.)¹ & Rebecca Nwanneka Obijindu²

^{1&2}Department of Guidance and Counselling Faculty of Education
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4055660>

Abstract

The study sought to determine parental involvement in child learning as a correlate of academic achievement of primary school pupils in Anambra State. The study was guided by five research questions and two hypotheses. The research design was correlational survey design. Disproportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 1,680 students from a population of 90,411 primary 5 school pupils in Anambra State. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled "Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ)". It has internal consistency reliability coefficient alpha of 0.78. The instrument was used to collect data which was administrated through direct delivery approach. Research questions 1, 2 and 3 were answered using percentages while Research question 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and the hypotheses were tested using t-test for correlation. Findings from the study revealed among others that there is a very low positive relationship existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in English Language. Also, the findings revealed that there is a very low negative relationship existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in Mathematics. Based on the findings, it is recommended among others that parents should be more involved in their children's learning by taking the leading role to support and assist their children in learning tasks such as take home assignments and going through their notes.

Key words: Parents involvement, child's learning, academic, achievement, pupils, primary school.

Introduction

Primary Education is a major foundation for social-economic and political development of a nation (FME, 2006). Hence, if the quality of education at such critical level is undermined, the schools may not give adequate knowledge, skills, and attitudes to pupils that a country need in its citizens in order to guarantee the role of education in national development. United Nations Education and Scientific Cultural Organisations (UNESCO, 2010) thus noted that most of the pupils that go through primary education in developing countries fail to master the basic

cognitive skills as shown by the poor performance in primary school examinations. This situation is much likely to be worse in countries that give and use public examination as the basis of important decision making about the educational and vocational future of pupils, of which Nigeria is a good example. The pupils' academic achievement in schools today has thus become a source of concern to stakeholders like parents, teachers, counsellors and others as their expectation of achieving optimum academic achievement seem not to have been met.

Academic achievement of school children could be explained in terms of the grades obtained in subjects, a course or group of courses. It is thus a measure of output whereby the main outputs in education are expressed in terms of learning, that is, changes in knowledge, skills and attitudes of individuals as a result of their experiences within the school system. According to Wilson (2012), academic achievement is defined as the outcome of education, the extent to which a student/pupil, teacher or institution have achieved their educational goals. It could also represent performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in such learning environment like primary, secondary and university (Fan, Williams & Wolters, 2011). However, in the context of this study, academic achievement is defined as achievement scores of pupils which indicate their scholastic standing in schools, using curricular-based criteria such as grades or performance scores on the achievement test in English Language and Mathematics as an educational benchmark.

Academic achievement according to Demir (2012) is categorised into two; high and low. High academic achievement is conceptualized as an optimal level of performance in academic tasks while low academic achievement is considered to be a deficient or poor performance in academic tasks. This means that a pupil who earns good grades or high scores in any of the subjects has achieved high in the academic field, while those with poor grades or lower scores indicates poor achievement in the academic field. Although it is the goal of every child to achieve high academically, such seem to have become a daunting task in Nigeria today owing to the consistent record of failures in public examinations, especially in those core subjects like Mathematics and English Language.

English Language and Mathematics are placed as compulsory subjects every pupil in the primary school is expected to pass. English language is widely used as a means of communication at every level of the Nigerian educational system. Consequently, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) pointed out that in each level of education, English shall be taught as a subject and English shall progressively be used as a medium of instruction. Mathematics on the other hand is perceived as the basis for modern scientific and technological developments which can also help pupils think in a clear and logical way, just as it can help them to solve simple practical problems, which they may meet in later life.

Notwithstanding the importance of English Language and Mathematics at the primary level of education in Nigeria as compulsory subjects required of every pupil to pass, Ubulom and Adoki (2016) noted that there are still fears in the minds of the education experts, scholars, parents and members of the society that primary school pupils are performing poorly academically, especially in core subjects like English language and Mathematics. This is based on the

observation of the falling standards of education in Nigeria, which has been attributed to the poor foundation of education being laid at the primary level of education (Sanubi & Akpotu, 2015).

The implication of such situation if not addressed is very serious as the quality of school leavers, at both primary and secondary levels has continued to, and may continue to deteriorate each year. Such situation certainly do not portend good omen neither for the pupils or any of the stakeholders. For instance, pupils' academic achievement, to some degree could determine whether a pupil will have the opportunity to continue his or her education (example, to attend secondary school or university) and based on the educational degrees one attains, influences their vocational career after schooling. Besides the relevance for an individual, academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity. Hence, the reason why enhancing the learners' academic achievement is an important concern for stakeholders like parents, teachers, and policymakers among others.

Many experts in the field of education have attempted to determine which factors have had the biggest influence on academic achievement of pupils. Among the factors identified which included educational policies at federal, state, local and school levels, parents involvement seems to have played some roles in the decline of academic achievement, especially at the primary level of education in Nigeria.

Education at the primary level is an indispensable means by which children are properly introduced to a complex and diverse world. At such critical stage, parents are indispensable in the children's daily lives and thus may play a significant role in their children's education. Hence, their involvement in the child's education may be one of the most important aspects of academic achievement which could improve the relationship between home and school. Thus, the study by Antoine (2015) revealed that actively involved parents help to increase and stimulate a child's interest in school and encourage their academic achievement.

Involvement of parents in their child's learning could be multifaceted and multidimensional. Hill and Tyson (2009) for instance used a classification which, as well as being thrifty, allows reasonable evaluation of evidence about parental involvement, indicating three meanings of the term: academic socialization, school-based involvement and home-based involvement. The first refers to the expectations, value, and usefulness the families confer on education and is the dimension which is most closely connected to academic performance. School based involvement includes attendance to parent-teacher, and other meetings, helping with school activities, and participation in the running of the school. Hill and Tyson (2009) and Jeynes (2016) indicated a significant, positive association between this dimension of involvement and academic performance.

On the other hand, parents' involvement at home covers support and cultural opportunities, communication about school matters and direct assistance with homework at home. This study in essence explores the two measures of home-based involvement: help and monitoring of homework, and communication and support of the educational process. Thus, in the context of this study, parental involvement is defined as parents interest in knowing the teacher, knowing what assignments are due, expecting quality work from the child, checking up

with questionable grades and occurrences, providing materials and time to do projects, expecting homework to be done or reviewed daily, knowing what the teacher expects and giving support. Parents generally have a strong role to play in their children's learning. Parents' involvement in their children's schooling could give a positive effect on their learning outcomes. Thus, it is believed that when parents are actively involved in their children's learning, their academic achievement will likely be enhanced. However, looking at primary school pupils academic achievement, available statistics have shown that the overall academic achievement rating of learners in Anambra State has remained on a steady decline, especially in core subjects like English language and Mathematics. Elekwa (2018) for instance observed that though the pupils had generally performed well in the First School leaving certificate examination, a close examination of the results showed that their performance in English Language and Mathematics was notably poor.

Research report according to Abuya, Ngware, Hungi, Mutisya, Nyariro, Mahuro and Oketch (2014) further revealed that learners who enjoyed parental involvement in their schooling significantly improved their educational aspirations than those not exposed to parental involvement package of the intervention. Abuya et al. report and those of the recent studies in Nigeria such as Akunne (2018) and Fajoku, Aluede and Ojugo (2016) have shown that parental participation in their children's schooling goes a long way in shaping and moulding their children's educational outcome. However, there is a limitation to the findings of these studies, as many of the studies carried out both within and outside Nigeria focused mostly on secondary school students. Few of the studies on primary school pupils failed to cover the geographical scope of the current study as they were done outside the current study area. This current study therefore seeks to add more evidence to the existing literature and further determine the relationship that exists between primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and the pupils academic achievement in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate parental involvement in child learning as a correlate of academic achievement of primary school pupils in Anambra State. Specifically the study sought to find out:

1. Scores of primary school pupils' parental involvement in their learning in Anambra State.
2. Academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in English Language in Anambra State.
3. Academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in Mathematics in Anambra State.
4. The relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State.
5. The relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the scores of primary school pupils' parental involvement in their learning in Anambra State?
2. What are the academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in English Language in Anambra State?
3. What are the academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in Mathematics in Anambra State?
4. What is the relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State?
5. What is the relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State
2. There is no significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State.

Method

The study was conducted using a correlational research design. The reason for using the research design was to establish the relationship that exists between variables; parental involvement in child's learning and academic achievement of primary school pupils in Anambra State. The sample for this study was 1,680 pupils selected from a population of 90,411 pupils in public primary schools in Anambra State. Multi-stage sampling method was employed in selecting the sample size.

The instruments for the study comprised of parental involvement questionnaire developed by the researcher and achievement score sheets derived from the schools. The instruments are described as follows: Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ); this contains 18 items on the specific things that parents do or need to do to show involvement with their children that are likely to affect the academic achievement in schools. In essence, it provides pupils' opportunity to rate their involvement with their parents and the parents' contribution to their success in schools. The questionnaire has a 4 point response options which ranged from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree, and has weighted values of 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively.

The pupils' achievement scores were derived from the score sheet comprising the pupils' achievement scores in Mathematics and English language, and indicating their individual names and scores in each of the subjects and end of the term. The achievement scores of the participants were reported as aggregate scores, ranging from 0 -100. All the participants for the study whose names appeared in the examination score sheets were administered the parental involvement questionnaire through direct delivery approach. The data collected for the research questions

were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r), while the null hypothesis was tested using t-test of correlation.

Results

In this section, the data collected from the field for this study were analysed and the summaries presented in tables and charts to highlight the findings as follows:

Research Question 1

What are the distribution scores of primary school pupils' parental involvement in their learning in Anambra State?

Figure 1: Distribution Scores of primary school pupils' parental involvement in their learning in Anambra State

Figure 1 shows that 420(29.0%) of primary school pupils rated their parental involvement low while 1027(71.0%) of primary school pupil rated their parental involvement high.

Research Question 2

What are the academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in English Language in Anambra State?

Figure 2: Distribution Scores of primary school pupils' English Language academic achievement in Anambra State

In figure 2 above, it was observed that 540(37.3%) and 536(37.0%) of the primary school pupils with the scores ranging from 40 to 59 have fair and average achievement in English language respectively, while 161(11.1%) and 179(12.4%) of the pupils who scored between 60to 100 have good and very good achievement in English language in Anambra state.

Research Question 3:What are the academic achievement scores of primary school pupils in Mathematics in Anambra State?

Figure 3: Distribution Scores of primary school pupils' Mathematics academic achievement in Anambra State

Figure 3 revealed that 716(49.4%) and 428(29.6%) of the primary school pupils with the scores ranging from 40 to 59 have fair and average achievement in Mathematics respectively, while 144(9.9%) of the pupils who scored between 0 to 39 have poor achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the relationship between parental involvement in learning and academic achievement of primary school pupils in English Language

Variables	N	Parental Involvement r	Eng. Achievement r	Remark
Parental Involvement	1448	1	.036	Very low Positive Relationship
English Lang. achievement	1448	.036	1	

Table 1 revealed that there is very low positive relationship of 0.036 existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in English Language in schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 5: What is the relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the relationship between parental involvement in learning and academic achievement of primary school pupils in Mathematics

Variables	N	Parental Involvement r	Mathematics Achievement r	Remark
Parental Involvement	1448	1	-.036	Very low negative Relationship
Mathematics achievement	1448	-.036	1	

Table 2 revealed that there is very low negative relationship of -0.030 existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in Mathematics in schools in Anambra State.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement of primary school pupils in English Language

Correlation Coefficient (γ)	N	df	pvalue	Cal.pvalue	Decision
.036	1448	1447	.05	.000	S

S = Significant

Table 3 revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and 1447df, the calculated r 0.036 has Pvalue 0.000 which is less than the critical Pvalue 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra State is rejected.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement of primary school pupils in Mathematics

Correlation Coefficient (γ)	N	df	pvalue	Cal.pvalue	Decision
-.030	1448	1447	.05	.197	NS

NS = Not Significant

Table 4 revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and 1447df, the calculated r -0.030 has calculated Pvalue 0.197 which is more than the critical Pvalue 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study are discussed as follows:

Parental Involvement on Primary School Pupils Learning

Findings of the study revealed that most of the primary school pupil rated their parental involvement in their learning high. This means that the parents are keenly involved in their children learning. The finding is consistent with Topor, Keane, Shelton and Calkins (2010) whose study examined parent involvement in a child's education. The result of the Topor, et al's study indicated a moderate to high level of parents' involvement in the child's education. The likely outcome of this is that when parents are highly involved in children's education, children are likely to perform and develop well in general and vice versa. According to Olatonye and Ogunkola (2008), this would mean that the parents are engaged in helping the children with homework, encouraging reading, school attendance, engaging in school based activities like attending Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings and having personal contact with teachers and counsellors to have an update on their children's capabilities.

Academic Achievement of Primary School Pupils

The findings of the study further revealed that majority of the primary school pupils have fair and average achievement in both English language and Mathematics respectively. This means that the pupils' academic achievement in English language was neither very good nor poor; rather, the performance was within average. This is an affirmation of the notion that there is a general low academic achievement among learners in Nigeria. The finding in this study agrees with Adeyemi (2014) and Akpan, Ojinnaka and Ekanem (2010). While Adeyemi conducted a comparative study of pupils' academic performance between private and public primary schools, Akpan, et al., compared the academic performance of primary school children with behavioural disorders. Both studies acknowledged that academic performance of pupils is below average. Similarly, Ubulom and Adoki (2016) study is consistent with the findings of the current study. The study revealed low level of academic performance among male and female pupils in written English in public primary schools.

Relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of primary school pupils

Findings of this study revealed that there is low positive relationship existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in English Language. The findings further revealed that the relationship between the primary school pupils' parental involvement and academic achievement in English Language is significant. This indicates that there is a strong association between parents' involvement in the learning of their primary school children which could lead to a higher or lower academic achievement of those children in subjects like English language.

This finding is consistent with Antoine (2015) whose study investigated whether or not there is a correlation between parental involvement and student academic achievement. The participants in the study were tested for correlations between the degree with which their parents are engaged in their academic lives and the academic success that they achieve as a result. The study by Antoine revealed that actively involved parents help to increase and stimulate a child's

interest in school and encourage their academic achievement. The finding is also consistent with Fajoku, Aluede and Ojugo (2016). Fajoku, Aluede and Ojugo's study investigated the relationship between parental involvement in children's education and the academic achievement of primary six pupils. The study revealed that parental involvement significantly influenced pupils' academic achievements in three core subjects, English Language, Mathematics and Integrated science in primary school and that the higher the parental involvement, the higher the achievement of pupils in the three core subjects.

Moreover, it was observed in this study that there is a very low negative relationship of -0.030 existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in Mathematics. The findings further revealed that the relationship between primary school pupils' parental involvement in the child's learning and academic achievement in Mathematics is not significant. This shows that there is an association between the two variables whereby an increase in one will lead to a significant increase in the other. This shows that pupils whose parents are involved in their education are more likely to perform better in mathematics and achieve more than other pupils whose parents are less involved in their learning.

The reason for these findings could be linked to many factors that influence parental involvement in their children's learning. Such factors have been categorized across both psychological and sociological dimensions. These factors according to Hoover-Dempsey, Battiato, Walker, Reed, Dejong and Jones (2015) include: Parental role construction, or parents' beliefs about what they should do in the context of their child's education. Parental self-efficacy for helping the child succeed in school or how much parents believed they could improve children's school outcomes; parents' perceptions of general invitations for involvement from the school and parents' life contexts such as socioeconomic status, culture, and family structure.

Furthermore, the results from the study revealed that active involvement from parents is vital in student's academic success. It showed that when parents were active in their children's school lives by volunteering in school, participating in school activities, and attending teacher-parent conferences, the children would achieve more in school. When parents were involved, higher expectations were placed on the pupil. Overall, the pupil's responses have a great bearing on the level of parental involvement efforts at their child's school and their child's academic success.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made:

There is a very low positive significant relationship existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in English Language. There is a non-significant very low negative relationship existing between the primary school pupils' parental involvement in learning and their academic achievements in Mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Guidance Counsellors and the school administrators should work together to help come up with stimulating and engaging activities in school, to get parents involved in their children's learning in schools as this would go a long way to help improve their academic achievement.
2. Parents should increase their effort in being involved in their children's learning by taking the leading role in supporting their children's learning endeavours, like take home assignments and going through their notes.

REFERENCES

- Abuya, B., Ngware, M., Hungi, N., Mutisya, M., Nyariro, M., Mahuro, G. & Oketch, M. (2014). *Community participation and after-school support to improve learning outcomes and transition to secondary school among disadvantaged girls*. Retrieved from <http://aphrc.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Improving-Learning-OutcomesMidterm-Report-2014.pdf>
- Adeyemi, S.B. (2014). Comparative study of pupils' academic performance between private and public primary schools. *World Journal of Education*, 4(4), 55-60.
- Akpan, M.U. Ojinnaka, N. C. & Ekanem, E. E. (2010). Academic Performance of school children with behavioural disorders in Uyo, Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2956301/#R7>
- Akunne, L. (2018). Relationship among parental involvement, school connectedness and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Anambra State. *Unpublished Master Thesis*, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Antoine, D.R. (2015). The correlation between parental involvement and student academic achievement. *Master Thesis*, Louisiana State University and Agricultural and Mechanical College. Retrieved from https://digitalcommons.lsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1184&context=gradschool_theses
- Elekwa, E. (2018, February 10). Anambra pupils get academic excellence award. *The Daily Trust*. Retrieved from <https://www.dailytrust.com.ng/Anambra-pupils-get-academic-excellence-award.html>
- Fajoku, S.A., Aluede, O. & Ojugo, A.I. (2016). Parental involvement as a correlate of academic achievement of primary school pupils in Edo State, Nigeria. *Research in Education*, 95(1), 33-43.
- Fan, W., Williams, C. M. & Wolters, C. A. (2012). Parental involvement in predicting school motivation: similar and differential effects across ethnic groups. *Journal of Educational Research*, 105(1), 21-35.

- Demir, H.W. (2012). Study behaviour and academic achievement: Relations and causal ordering. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 81, 59-77.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2006). *Country report of Nigeria*. International Conference on Education, 46th session, Geneva,
- Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria (2015). *Digest of educational statistics*. Abuja: Federal Minister of Education
- Hill, N.E. & Tyson, D.F. (2009). Parental involvement in middle school: A meta analytic assessment of the strategies that promote achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 45(3), 740-763.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K.V., Battiato, A.C., Walker, J.M., Reed, R.P., DeJong, J.M., & Jones, K.P. (2015). Parental Involvement in homework. *Educational Psychologist*, 36, 3, 195-209
- Jeynes, W.H. (2016). A meta-analysis: The relationship between parental involvement and African American school outcomes. *Journal of Black Studies*, 47(3), 195-216.
- Olatoye, R.A. & Agbatogun, A.O. (2009). Parental involvement as a correlate of pupils 'achievement in mathematics and science in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Educational Research and Review*, 4(10), 457-464.
- Sanubi, F.A. & Akpotu, N.E. (2015). The Nigeria education system and vision 20: 2020: A critical development planning perspective. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 7(2), 26-38.
- Topor, D.R., Keane, S.P., Shelton, T.L. & Calkins, S.B. (2010). Parent involvement and student academic performance: A multiple mediational analysis. *JPrevInterv Community*, 38(3), 183-197.
- Ubulom, W.J. & Adoki, M.I. (2016). Academic performance of public and private primary school pupils in written English in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Innovative Language, Literature & Art Studies* 4(2), 20-27.
- UNESCO, (2010). *Education For All Global Monitoring Report 2010: Reaching the Marginalized*. Paris: UNESCO
- Wilson, J.G. (2012). Students' mathematics performance and motivation to learn mathematics: Relationship and gender differences among Kenya's secondary school students in Nairobi and Rift Valley provinces. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 23(5), 487-499.